

QUINOLINE DERIVATIVES. PART I.

BY TEJENDRA NATH GHOSH.

In a previous communication (Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 27) it has been shown that the thiohydantoin (I) condenses with *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde and the reduction of the resulting product yields a quinoline derivative.

(I)

The thiohydantoin is readily hydrolysed by alkali to the corresponding thiocarbamidoacetic acid derivative (II). When treated with acetic anhydride, the compound (II) is readily converted into the thiazole derivative (III), which, because of the presence of a reactive methylene group, condenses with *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde to yield the compound (IV). The reduction of (IV) with zinc dust and acetic acid yields the quinoline derivative (V).

(II)

(III)

(IV)

(V)

Reference may be made to the pharmacological examination of thiazole derivatives (Suter and Johnson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 52, 1585). 2-Thiocarbonyl-4-keto-5 : 5-diethyltetrahydrothiazole has been found to have a narcotic effect slightly greater than that of veronal but with a quicker recovery (Leonard, *Medd. K. Ventenskapskad. Nobel-Inst.*, 1922, 4, No. 14, 1-13). In view of the chemotherapeutical importance of thiazole derivatives and of the presence of thiazole ring in vitamin B₁ (Williams, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 58, 1063; Williams and Cline, *ibid.*, 1936,

58, 1504), the present synthesis of thiazole-quinoline derivatives is of considerable interest. Compounds (III) and (V), (where R = phenetyl) have been synthesised. These compounds are expected to possess antipyretic and analgesic properties (*cf.* Suter and Johnson, *loc. cit.*).

EXPERIMENTAL.

p-Tolylthiocarbamidoacetic Acid (II, R = *p*-tolyl).—The compound (I, R = *p*-tolyl, 3.8 g.) was dissolved in alcohol (100 c. c.) containing 1.3 g. of caustic potash. The rose-coloured clear solution was heated under reflux for about 1 hour and evaporated to dryness. The solid obtained was the potassium salt of *p*-tolylthiocarbamidoacetic acid. The free acid was obtained as a colourless precipitate when a cold aqueous solution of the potassium salt was acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. It crystallised from hot water in colourless rectangular plates, m. p. 147–148° (decomp.), yield 3 g. (Found : N, 12.35. C₁₀H₁₂O₂N₂S requires N, 12.50 per cent). It is soluble in sodium bicarbonate solution.

2-Keto-5-*p*-tolylaminodihydro-1:4-thiazole (III, R = *p*-tolyl).—An acetic anhydride solution of the above compound (II, *p*-tolyl) was heated under reflux for about 1 hour and cooled, when a crystalline precipitate came out, which further crystallised from alcohol in brownish plates, m. p. 157–58°, yield almost quantitative. (Found : N, 13.27. C₁₀H₁₀ON₂S requires N, 13.59 per cent). It is not desulphurised by yellow oxide of mercury, indicating that the sulphur atom is cyclic. It is insoluble in cold alkali but on long standing goes into solution and the alkaline solution, on acidification, yields the original acid (II, R = *p*-tolyl).

2-Keto-3-*o*-nitrobenzal-5-*p*-tolylaminodihydro-1:4-thiazole (IV, R = *p*-tolyl).—An acetic anhydride solution of the compound (III, R = *p*-tolyl, 6.2 g.) and *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde (4.5 g.) was heated under reflux for about 2 hours. The clear solution, on cooling, deposited a crystalline mass which further crystallised from glacial acetic acid in yellowish needles, m. p. 200–201°, yield 7 g. (Found : N, 12.18. C₁₇H₁₃O₃N₃S requires N, 12.39 per cent).

Reduction of the above Compound (IV, R = p-tolyl) : Formation of 5-p-Tolylaminothiazole-2 : 3 (2' : 3')-quinoline (V, R = p-tolyl).—A solution of the above compound (IV, R = *p*-tolyl, 6 g.) in acetic acid (100 c. c.) was boiled with zinc dust until it became colourless; it was then filtered and diluted with much water. The solid, thus obtained, was filtered, extracted with hot alcohol, washed with dilute hydrochloric

acid and water and was finally crystallised from alcohol in colourless plates m. p. 191-92°, yield 0.5 g. (Found : N, 14.22. $C_{17}H_{13}N_3S$ requires N, 14.43 per cent). It is soluble in strong acids but insoluble in alkali.

The same compound (m. p. 191-192°) is obtained, if the reduction is carried out with granulated tin and hydrochloric acid.

p-Phenethylthiocarbamidoacetic Acid (II, R = *p*-phenetyl).—A dilute alcoholic solution of glycine (2.3 g.) and *p*-phenethylisothiocyanate (5.4 g.) was heated under reflux for about an hour and then evaporated almost to dryness. The solid was then treated with cold dilute alkali; the rose coloured alkaline solution, on acidification with hydrochloric acid, gave a precipitate which crystallised from alcohol in colourless rectangular plates, m. p. 134-35° (decomp.), yield 4.5 g. (Found : N, 10.85. $C_{11}H_{14}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 11.02 per cent). It is readily soluble in aqueous sodium bicarbonate solution.

2-Keto-5-*p*-phenethylaminodihydro-1:4-thiazole (III, R = *p*-phenetyl).—The method of preparation was the same as in the case of the previous compound (III, R = *p*-tolyl). The compound crystallised from glacial acetic acid in brownish rectangular plates, m. p. 193-94°. (Found : N, 11.61. $C_{11}H_{12}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 11.86 per cent). It is insoluble in alkali and is not desulphurised by yellow oxide of mercury.

2-Keto-3-*o*-nitrobenzal-5-*p*-phenethylaminodihydro-1:4-thiazole (IV, R = *p*-phenetyl).—The method of preparation was the same as in the case of the previous compound (IV, R = *p*-tolyl). The compound crystallised from glacial acetic acid in yellowish shining rectangular plates, m. p. 177-78°. (Found : N, 11.12. $C_{18}H_{15}O_4N_3S$ requires N, 11.38 per cent).

Reduction of the above Compound (IV, R = p-phenetyl): Formation of 5-p-Phenethylaminothiazole-2:3(2':3')-quinoline (V, R = p-phenetyl).—The method of procedure was the same as in the case of the previous compound (V, R = *p*-tolyl). The compound crystallised from alcohol in brownish white rectangular plates, m. p. 175°. (Found : N, 13.27. $C_{18}H_{15}ON_3S$ requires N, 13.08 per cent). It is insoluble in alkali and is not desulphurised by yellow oxide of mercury.

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